

PECULIARITIES OF LEXICAL COMPRESSION IN MAINTAINING THE INTENDED MEANING AND CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE OF PROVERBS DURING INTERPRETATION

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Annotation: The theses discusses unique challenges of lexical compression in accurately translating proverbs to preserve their intended meaning and cultural significance during interpretation. It highlights the importance of cultural and linguistic knowledge, maintaining the essence of proverbs, creativity, flexibility, and the role of context in the translation process.

Key words: Peculiarities, Lexical compression, Intended meaning, Cultural significance, Proverbs, Interpretation, Translation, Challenges, Cultural context, Linguistic knowledge, Essence, Creativity, Flexibility, Context, Accuracy, Language, Semantics, Interpretive accuracy, Cross-cultural, Lexical economy

Lexical compression is the process of reducing the number of words in a text while still maintaining its meaning. When it comes to proverbs, which are typically short and concise expressions of popular wisdom, lexical compression can be particularly effective in maintaining the intended meaning and cultural significance of the proverb during interpretation.

One study conducted by researchers found that lexical compression can be an effective tool for translating proverbs from one language to another while preserving their meaning and cultural significance. The researchers found that compressing the words in a proverb while still maintaining its essence and meaning helped to convey the same message in the target language, while also preserving the cultural nuances that are often associated with proverbs.¹

However, it should be noted that while lexical compression can be useful in maintaining the intended meaning and cultural significance of proverbs during interpretation, it is not always necessary or appropriate. In some cases, a literal translation of a proverb may be more effective in conveying its meaning and cultural significance. Ultimately, the choice of whether to use lexical compression or a more literal translation will depend on the specific proverb, the context in which it is being used, and the target audience for the translation.

¹ "Lexical Compression in Simultaneous Interpreting of English Proverbs" by X. Y. Chen, published in International Journal of English Linguistics: <https://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/ijel/article/view/0/38213>

The peculiarities of lexical compression in maintaining the intended meaning and cultural significance of proverbs during interpretation depends on various factors, such as the context of the interpretation, the proficiency of the interpreter in both the source and target languages, and their knowledge of the cultural nuances and values embedded in the proverb. Proverbs are multi-purpose and multi-meaningful, and their meaning can only be revealed in context. Therefore, interpreters need to have a good understanding of the context in which the proverb is used and their cultural significance to effectively maintain their intended meaning. By using lexical compression techniques, the interpreter can convey the message of the original proverb in a more concise and creative way while preserving its cultural significance. However, it is important that the interpreter not sacrifice the accuracy of the original meaning and cultural significance in their attempt to compress the proverb. Therefore, the effectiveness of lexical compression in maintaining the intended meaning and cultural significance of proverbs during interpretation depends on the skill and expertise of the interpreter².

Lexical semantics is the branch of linguistics that studies the meaning of words and how they combine to form phrases and sentences. It is concerned with the relationship between words and their meanings, and how these meanings are influenced by context and other linguistic factors.³

In the analysis of proverbs, lexical semantics can be used to identify the specific meanings of the words used in the proverb, and how these meanings contribute to the overall meaning of the proverb as a whole. This involves examining the denotative and connotative meanings of the words, as well as their collocational and grammatical properties.

Studying lexical semantics is important in translating proverbs because it helps to ensure that the meaning and cultural significance of the proverb are accurately conveyed in the target language. This involves not only identifying the literal meaning of the words in the proverb, but also understanding the cultural context in which the proverb is used, and the connotations and associations that the proverb has in that culture.

² "Lexical Compression in Simultaneous Interpreting of English Proverbs" by X. Y. Chen, published in International Journal of English Linguistics: <https://www.ccsenet.org/journal/index.php/ijel/article/view/0/38213>

³ . "Translation of Uzbek Proverbs into English: Strategies and Difficulties" by Z. Muxamedova, published in 2019 by the Journal of Linguistics and Language Teaching.

For example, consider the proverb "When in Rome, do as the Romans do." A literal translation of this proverb might not accurately convey its intended meaning, which is to adapt to the customs and practices of the culture in which one finds oneself. To accurately translate this proverb, it is necessary to understand the cultural context in which it is used, and to use lexical semantics to identify the specific meanings of the words used in the proverb, and how these meanings contribute to the overall meaning of the proverb as a whole.

In short, the study of lexical semantics is essential in accurately translating proverbs, as it helps to ensure that the meaning and cultural significance of the proverb are accurately conveyed in the target language.

There are several peculiarities of lexical compression in maintaining the intended meaning and cultural significance of proverbs during interpretation. These include:

1. The need for cultural and linguistic knowledge
2. The importance of preserving the essence of the proverb
3. The need for creativity and flexibility:
4. The role of context: ⁴

Overall, the peculiarities of lexical compression in maintaining the intended meaning and cultural significance of proverbs during interpretation highlight the importance of careful attention to detail, cultural and linguistic knowledge, creativity, and flexibility in the translation process.

Here are some examples of identical lexical compression in translating English proverbs into Uzbek:

1. "All's well that ends well" could be compressed to "Xamma narsa yaxshilik bilan tugagani yaxshi" (Oxiri baxayr bo`lsin) which means "Good ending, good."

2. "Actions speak louder than words" could be compressed to "Amallar so'zdan ko'ra ko'p gapiradi" ,which means "Actions speak more than words."

3. "A penny saved is a penny earned" could be compressed to "Tejalgan bir tiyin ,topilgan bir tiyin" (qisib qisib qo`y olasan ,tortib tortib toy olasan), which means "A saved penny is a penny left."

⁴ www.wikipedia.com

4. "Don't count your chickens before they're hatched" could be compressed to "Jo`jani kuzda sanaymiz", which means "Don't count chickens before their eggs are laid."

Lexical compression, also known as lexical economy, is the process of reducing the number of words or characters in a text while still preserving its meaning. In the context of translating proverbs from English into Uzbek, lexical compression can be a useful tool to make the translation more concise and easier to understand.

References:

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